

Monohydroxytrifluoroborates and Double Fluoroborates

A. K. Sengupta and S. K. Mukherjee

The monohydroxytrifluoroborates of alkali and alkaline earth metals have been described in the literature^{1,2,3}.

By the action of various fluorides and hydrofluoric acid on boric acid in aqueous solution we have been able to isolate the monohydroxytrifluoroborates of Rb^+ , Cs^+ , $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4]^+\text{Ni}^{2+}$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{py})_4]^{2+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{3+}$, and nitron. Contrary to the earlier report¹ the nitron salt has been found to be slightly soluble. The nickel salts are respectively penta- and hexahydrated. Analytical data of some of these are reported here. $\text{Rb BF}_3(\text{OH})$ requires Rb 50.2, B 6.38, F 33.41%; Found 50.43, B 6.38, F 33.10%. $\text{Cs BF}_3(\text{OH})$ requires Cs 61.03, B 4.97, F 26.10%; Found Cs 61.17, B 4.89, F 25.72%; Calc. for $[\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_4][\text{BF}_3(\text{OH})]$: N 7.53, B 5.82, F 30.68%; Found N 7.54, B 6.0, F 30.36%.

By following the above procedure instead of the monohydroxytrifluoroborates we have obtained double fluoroborates corresponding to the formula $\text{M BF}_4 \cdot \text{M BF}_3(\text{OH}) \times \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{M} = \frac{1}{2} [\text{Mn}, \text{Co}, \text{Zn}, \text{Cd}, \text{Cu}(\text{pyridine})_4]$ etc. The pyridinium and nitron salt of this series have also been isolated. Analytical results for the manganese and cobalt compound: Calc. for $\text{Co}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{Co}(\text{BF}_3\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Co 17.94, B 6.57, F 40.37; Found Co 17.5, B 6.70, F 40.73%; Calc. for $\text{Mn}(\text{BF}_4)_2 \cdot \text{Mn}(\text{BF}_3\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$: Mn 16.90, B 6.63, F 40.85%; Found Mn 16.60, B 6.94, F 40.3%.

The IR-spectra of some of the compounds have been recorded. Further work is in progress and the details will be reported later.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY OF KALYANI,
KALYANI, WEST BENGAL.

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